

Length of arc joining two ends of diameter is always greater than the diameter in semi-circle.

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Abstract: Circles are amazing objects in regular geometry. Through this paper, we report that the length of arc in a semi-circle joining two ends of diameter is always less than the diameter, with experimental verification.

Keywords: Circle, Semi-Circle, Arc Diameter

Introduction:

Line of diameter passes from center of circle to two ends in circumference of circle. Let us consider three circles.

fig: a

fig:b

fig: c

In the above figures, straight line AB represents the diameter, and it divides the circles in two semi-circles.

From figures

Length of Diameter AB	Length of Arc AB	Remarks

Conclusion:

Thus from above calculations, it is evidently clear that the length of diameter joining two ends of circle is always less than the arc.

References:

[1] Arjun Dahal. (2021). Un-Anthology: Dark Side of NOT Grammar. Zenodo.
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